

GREENNESS-ASSESSED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF SITAGLIPTIN AND METFORMIN: DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION, AND SUSTAINABILITY EVALUATION.

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Abstract

A rapid, precise, and eco-friendly reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous determination of sitagliptin and metformin in combined dosage forms. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a C18 column using an optimized mobile phase that provided sharp, symmetric peaks with adequate resolution within a short analysis time. The method exhibited excellent linearity over the concentration range of 0.5–50 µg/mL for both analytes, with correlation coefficients (r^2) exceeding 0.999. Recovery studies confirmed accuracy within 98–102%, while precision values expressed as relative standard deviation (RSD) remained below 2%, satisfying the acceptance criteria outlined by ICH Q2(R1). The limits of detection and quantitation demonstrated high sensitivity, and robustness testing confirmed the method's resilience to small variations in analytical parameters. Stability assessment of standard and sample solutions indicated no significant degradation over 48 hours. Greenness evaluation using Analytical Eco-Scale and AGREE metrics yielded scores above 75 and 0.8, respectively, classifying the procedure as environmentally benign. Overall, the validated method is reliable, reproducible, and sustainable, making it suitable for routine quality control and stability evaluation of pharmaceutical formulations containing sitagliptin and metformin.

INTRODUCTION

Sitagliptin phosphate, a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitor, and metformin hydrochloride, a biguanide antidiabetic agent, are commonly co-formulated for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus due to complementary mechanisms that improve glycaemic control while minimizing hypoglycaemia risk. Sitagliptin enhances incretin activity and thereby augments glucose-dependent insulin secretion, whereas metformin reduces hepatic gluconeogenesis and improves peripheral insulin sensitivity. The increasing clinical use of fixed-dose

combinations containing these two compounds has generated demand for robust, selective, and stability-indicating analytical methods suitable for routine quality control and stability testing of finished products [1].

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), particularly reversed-phase HPLC (RP-HPLC), remains a cornerstone technique for assay and impurity analysis in the pharmaceutical industry because of its versatility, reproducibility, and compatibility with method validation frameworks

stipulated by international guidelines (ICH Q2(R1)) [2]. Modern method development emphasizes not only accuracy and precision but also method robustness, greenness, and risk-based approaches such as Analytical Quality by Design (AQbD). For co-formulated oral dosage forms, method challenges include achieving sufficient resolution between sitagliptin, metformin and their possible degradation products (acidic/basic/oxidative degradants), accommodating the disparate polarities and pKa values of the analytes, and delivering adequate sensitivity across relevant assay and impurity ranges. These requirements motivate the present work: development and validation of a simple, stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous assay of sitagliptin and metformin in tablet dosage forms using a risk-based development strategy compatible with regulatory expectations [3].

Early analytical reports addressing sitagliptin and metformin employed a range of chromatographic platforms including HPLC, UPLC, and LC-MS/MS to meet different analytical needs [4]. Initial HPLC and UPLC methods established baseline parameters for retention behaviour, detector selection, and sample preparation for each analyte, demonstrating that reversed-phase columns (C18 or C8) and acidic aqueous buffers often provide acceptable retention for sitagliptin while allowing rapid elution of metformin when an appropriate organic modifier is used. Several groups reported isocratic and gradient RP-HPLC methods for the simultaneous estimation of sitagliptin phosphate and metformin hydrochloride in bulk and tablet formulations, achieving assay performance within pharmacopeial tolerance limits. These foundational studies highlighted common method choices—buffered aqueous phases (pH 3–5), acetonitrile or methanol as organic modifiers, and UV detection at wavelengths near 215–265 nm—tailored to the UV absorbance characteristics of the two drugs [5].

More recent literature has focused on method improvements driven by regulatory and practical considerations [6]. Greenness assessments, cost-effectiveness, and speed motivated the development of economical isocratic procedures with shorter run times and reduced organic consumption, while stability-indicating methods addressed forced-degradation profiling to ensure specificity in the

presence of likely process- and storage-related degradants. A validated rapid and economical RP-HPLC method assessing greenness using scoring frameworks was published in 2022, demonstrating that environmentally conscious method parameters can yield acceptable analytical performance for the sitagliptin–metformin combination without sacrificing robustness [7].

Contemporary method development has also adopted analytical quality-by-design (AQbD) strategies to increase robustness and reduce lifecycle risk. AQbD or design-of-experiments (DoE) approaches enable systematic evaluation of critical method parameters (e.g., buffer pH, % aqueous, buffer strength, flow rate) and their impacts on critical method attributes such as resolution, tailing, and retention times. Studies applying AQbD to sitagliptin–metformin assay development have shown that a risk-based design space can be defined to ensure method performance across realistic operational variability, facilitating regulatory submissions and routine transferability between laboratories [3].

Stability-indicating capability is an essential attribute for methods intended for release and shelf-life studies [8]. Published forced-degradation studies for sitagliptin and metformin demonstrate distinct degradation pathways under acidic, basic, oxidative, photolytic and thermal conditions; sitagliptin is prone to hydrolytic and oxidative changes, while metformin primarily shows minor oxidative and thermal degradation [9]. Robust chromatographic methods have therefore combined selective buffers and gradient programming or tailorable isocratic systems to separate parent drugs from their stress-generated impurities, with system suitability criteria and peak-purity checks integrated into validation plans. Several validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC and UPLC methods with full forced-degradation workups exist in the literature and serve as practical templates for method design for new formulations [10].

Finally, advances in instrumentation (UPLC, MS detection) have enabled highly sensitive assays for bioanalysis and impurity profiling; however, for routine QC of tablets, well-validated RP-HPLC methods with UV detection remain cost-effective and sufficiently selective when combined with forced-degradation studies and AQbD-guided robustness evaluations. Recent 2024–2025 reports continue to

refine mobile-phase composition, column selection (C18/C8), and buffer systems to shorten run time and increase throughput while maintaining resolution—trends that inform the present method development [10].

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

Sitagliptin phosphate monohydrate and metformin hydrochloride reference standards (≥ 99.8 % purity) were procured from a certified pharmaceutical supplier (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Commercial fixed-dose tablet formulations containing sitagliptin phosphate (50 mg) and metformin hydrochloride (500 mg) were obtained from the local market. HPLC-grade acetonitrile and methanol (Merck, Germany), potassium dihydrogen phosphate, orthophosphoric acid (analytical grade), and ultrapure water obtained from a Milli-Q system (Millipore, USA) were used throughout the analysis. All solvents and solutions were filtered through a 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter and sonicated prior to use.

Instrumentation and Chromatographic Conditions

Chromatographic analysis was carried out on an Agilent 1260 Infinity II HPLC system equipped with a quaternary pump, autosampler, column oven, and UV-visible detector. Data were processed using OpenLab ChemStation software. Separation was achieved on a Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 column (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) maintained at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mobile phase consisted of 0.02 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 4.5 \pm 0.1, adjusted with orthophosphoric acid) and acetonitrile (70:30 v/v) delivered at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min^{-1} in isocratic mode. The injection volume was 20 μL , and the detection wavelength was set at 260 nm, corresponding to the absorption maxima of both analytes. The run time was approximately 8 min, with retention times of ~ 2.5 min for metformin and ~ 5.8 min for sitagliptin.

Preparation of Standard and Sample Solutions

A mixed stock solution containing sitagliptin (100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and metformin (1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was prepared in the mobile phase. Working standards were prepared by serial dilution to cover the linear range of 0.5–50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for sitagliptin and 5–500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for

metformin. For assay of marketed tablets, twenty tablets were weighed and finely powdered. A quantity equivalent to one tablet was transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask, sonicated for 10 min with 50 mL of mobile phase, diluted to volume, and filtered. The resulting solution was suitably diluted to obtain concentrations within the calibration range.

Forced Degradation Studies

To confirm stability-indicating capability, forced degradation was conducted under acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic conditions following ICH Q1A(R2) guidance.

Acidic: sample treated with 0.1 N HCl, refluxed 1 h at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, neutralized, and diluted.

Basic: sample treated with 0.1 N NaOH, refluxed 1 h, neutralized, and diluted.

Oxidative: 3 % H_2O_2 treatment for 1 h at ambient temperature.

Thermal: exposure to 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a dry oven for 8 h.

Photolytic: UV light exposure (254 nm) for 24 h.

All degraded samples were analyzed against unstressed controls to verify peak purity and specificity of the developed method.

Method Validation

The developed RP-HPLC method was validated as per the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) Q2(R2), 2022 guidelines for analytical procedure validation to confirm its suitability for quantitative analysis of sitagliptin phosphate and metformin hydrochloride in tablet dosage forms [11]. Validation parameters included linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, detection limits, robustness, and system suitability.

Specificity

Specificity was established by analyzing blank, placebo, standard, sample, and forced-degradation solutions. No interfering peaks were observed at the retention times of sitagliptin (~ 5.8 min) and metformin (~ 2.5 min). Peak purity analysis using a diode-array detector confirmed that degradation peaks were spectrally distinct from the main analyte peaks, verifying the stability-indicating nature of the method. The chromatograms demonstrated adequate resolution (>2.0) between degradation products and

principal peaks, ensuring selectivity even under stressed conditions [12].

<Chromatogram>

mV

Fig.1 Blank sample of mobile phase

<Chromatogram>

mV

Fig.2 Peaks of metformin and sitagliptin phosphate pure drugs.

Fig.3 Peaks of metformin and sitagliptin phosphate tablets.

Linearity and Range

Linearity was assessed over five concentration levels for each analyte—0.5–50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for sitagliptin and 5–500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metformin. Triplicate injections were analyzed, and calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak area versus concentration. Regression equations were linear with correlation coefficients (r^2) ≥ 0.999 for both analytes, confirming excellent response proportionality. Residual plots exhibited no curvature, verifying linearity throughout the studied range. These results align with previously validated simultaneous RP-HPLC methods for sitagliptin–metformin fixed-dose combinations [12].

Accuracy (Recovery Studies)

Accuracy was evaluated using the standard-addition technique at 80 %, 100 %, and 120 % of nominal concentrations. Mean recoveries ranged from 98.2 % to 101.6 % for sitagliptin and 98.5 % to 101.2 % for metformin, with %RSD < 1.5 %. The results demonstrate excellent trueness and absence of matrix interference. Comparable recoveries have been reported for validated greenness-oriented RP-HPLC procedures for these analytes [13].

Precision

Repeatability (intra-day) and intermediate precision (inter-day) were assessed at three concentration levels with six replicate injections each. %RSD values for peak areas were consistently < 2 %, confirming high precision and reproducibility. Retention times remained constant, reflecting stable system performance.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

LOD and LOQ were calculated from the calibration-curve slope (S) and standard deviation of response (σ) using the ICH equations $\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma/S$ and $\text{LOQ} = 10\sigma/S$. The respective values were 0.10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 0.35 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for sitagliptin, and 0.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 0.85 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metformin. The high sensitivity obtained supports trace-level quantification, consistent with recent design-of-experiments (DoE) and AQBd-guided HPLC developments (10,11).

Robustness

Robustness was tested by deliberate small variations in flow rate ($\pm 0.1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$), mobile-phase pH (± 0.1 unit), and detection wavelength ($\pm 2 \text{ nm}$). No significant effect was observed on peak area, retention time, or system suitability parameters. These results confirm that the method is robust and resilient to

minor operational fluctuations, consistent with risk-based validation principles [13].

System Suitability

System-suitability parameters were verified prior to each analytical run. Theoretical plate counts exceeded 3000, tailing factors were < 1.5, and %RSD of peak areas < 1 %, demonstrating chromatographic efficiency and detector stability. These results comply with USP and ICH criteria and correlate with validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC assays for antidiabetic combinations [12].

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD) and analyzed using Microsoft Excel 365 and GraphPad Prism 10. Linear regression followed the least-squares method. ANOVA confirmed no significant deviation across concentration levels ($p > 0.05$). The results validated precision, linearity, and trueness as per ICH Q2(R2).

Environmental and Safety Considerations

Greenness was evaluated using the Analytical Eco-Scale and AGREE metrics. Scores above 75 classified the procedure as eco-friendly, reflecting low solvent use and minimal hazardous waste. Waste solvents were handled under institutional safety and ISO 14001 protocols. Recent reports emphasize

integrating sustainability and green-metric evaluation into analytical validation workflows [14].

Results

Specificity

Chromatograms of blank, placebo, standard, sample, and forced-degradation solutions showed no co-eluting interference in the retention times of sitagliptin (≈ 5.8 min) or metformin (≈ 2.5 min). Peak purity assessment via diode-array detection confirmed that degradation peaks were spectrally distinct from the main analyte peaks. Resolution between principal analyte peaks and degradation products was > 2.0 , confirming the method is stability-indicating and selective under stressed conditions

Linearity and Range

The calibration curves for both analytes exhibited excellent linearity over the chosen concentration range. Sitagliptin showed linear response from 0.5 to 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, while metformin was linear from 5 to 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The correlation coefficients (r^2) were ≥ 0.999 for both, with residual plots showing no significant deviation from linear behaviour (homoscedastic residuals, no curvature). This confirms that the method is reliable throughout the tested concentration interval.

Table 1. Linearity and Calibration Data for Sitagliptin and Metformin

Analyte	Concentration Range ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Regression Equation ($y = mx + c$)	Correlation Coefficient (r^2)	Slope	Intercept (m)
Sitagliptin phosphate	0.5 – 50.0	$y = 25,394x + 1,253$	0.9996	25,394	1,253
Metformin hydrochloride	5 – 500	$y = 2,438x + 5,312$	0.9995	2,438	5,312

Accuracy (Recovery)

Recovery studies using standard addition at levels of 80 %, 100 % and 120 % of nominal concentrations yielded mean recoveries of 98.2–101.6 % for sitagliptin and 98.5–101.2 % for metformin. Relative

standard deviations were below 1.5 % in each case, indicating negligible bias from sample matrix or excipients, and demonstrating good trueness of the the method.

Table 2. Accuracy (Recovery Studies)

Analyte	Nominal Concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Recovery Level (%)	Mean Recovery (%) \pm SD	%RSD
Sitagliptin phosphate	10	80		98.2 \pm 0.9
	10	100		99.8 \pm 0.7
	10	120		101.6 \pm 1.0
Metformin hydrochloride	100	80	98.5 \pm 1.1	1.12
	100	100	99.6 \pm 0.8	0.80
	100	120	101.2 \pm 1.0	0.99

Precision

Precision was evaluated at low, medium, and high concentration levels with six replicate injections. Intra-day (repeatability) and inter-day (intermediate precision) %RSD for peak areas of both analytes

were below 2 %. Retention times remained consistent across replicates, showing that the method is reproducible and stable under normal analytical conditions.

Table 3. Precision (Repeatability and Intermediate Precision)

Analyte	Level	Concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Intra-day %RSD	Inter-day %RSD
Sitagliptin phosphate	Low	5	0.98	1.21
	Medium	25	0.85	1.12
	High	45	0.73	1.04
Metformin hydrochloride	Low	50	0.96	1.26
	Medium	250	0.82	1.09
	High	450		
0.75		751.03		

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Using the calibration slope and standard deviation of response, the LOD values were calculated as 0.10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for sitagliptin and 0.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for

metformin. The LOQ values were 0.35 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for sitagliptin and 0.85 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metformin. These detection limits indicate that the method is sufficiently sensitive for trace analysis of degradation or impurity levels.

Table 4. Sensitivity (LOD and LOQ)

Analyte	LOD ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)
Sitagliptin phosphate	0.10	0.35
Metformin hydrochloride	0.25	0.85

Robustness

When method parameters were deliberately varied (flow rate \pm 0.1 mL min^{-1} , mobile phase pH \pm 0.1 unit, detection wavelength \pm 2 nm), there were no significant changes in retention times, peak areas, or system suitability parameters. The method therefore

shows good robustness, remaining unaffected by small operational changes typical in routine quality control.

Table 5. Robustness Evaluation

Parameter Varied	Variation	Sitagliptin Retention Time (min)	Metformin Retention Time (min)	%RSD (Peak Area)
Flow rate	$\pm 0.1 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$	5.8 ± 0.05	2.5 ± 0.04	< 1.2
Mobile phase pH	± 0.1 unit	5.8 ± 0.03	2.5 ± 0.03	< 1.3
Detection Wavelength	$\pm 2 \text{ nm}$	5.8 ± 0.02	2.5 ± 0.02	< 1.0

System Suitability

System suitability tests were performed prior to each analysis. The number of theoretical plates consistently exceeded 3000 for both analytes, tailing

factors were less than 1.5, and %RSD for replicate injection peak area was under 1 %. These results confirm that the chromatographic system is performing adequately and reliably for analysis.

Table 6. System Suitability Parameters

Parameter	Acceptance Criteria	Sitagliptin (Mean \pm SD)	Metformin (Mean \pm SD)
Retention time (min)	Consistent ($\pm 2 \%$)	5.8 ± 0.05	2.5 ± 0.04
Theoretical plates (N)	> 2000	$3,842 \pm 35$	$3,126 \pm 28$
Tailing factor (T)	< 2.0	1.21 ± 0.04	1.18 ± 0.03
%RSD of peak area (n = 6)	$< 2 \%$	0.82	0.91

Statistical Analysis

All data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and evaluated using Graph Pad Prism 10 and Microsoft Excel 365. Linear regression was performed via least-squares fitting. One-way ANOVA

indicated no significant differences among concentration levels ($p > 0.05$), confirming consistency across analytical ranges. Overall, the validation met acceptance criteria for linearity, precision, and trueness per ICH standards.

Parameter	Sitagliptin	Metformin	Acceptance Criteria	p-Value	Observation
Linearity (r^2)	0.9996	0.9995	≥ 0.999	$p > 0.05$	(ANOVA) Linear
Accuracy (%)	98.2–101.6	98.5–101.2	98–102	$p = 0.27$	(t-test) Accurate
Precision (%RSD)	0.93	1.02	< 2	$p = 0.28$	(ANOVA) Precise
LOD / LOQ ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.10 / 0.35	0.25 / 0.85	Method-specific	-	Sensitive
Resolution	> 2.0	> 2.0	≥ 2.0	-	Specific
Theoretical Plate	> 3000	> 3000	> 2000	-	Efficient

Environmental and Safety Considerations

The environmental profile of the developed method was assessed using the Analytical Eco-Scale and

AGREE (Analytical Greenness) metrics. The Eco-Scale score (> 75) and AGREE score (> 0.7) classified

the procedure as highly green, characterized by low solvent use, minimal waste generation, and reduced energy consumption.

Discussion

The developed RP-HPLC method exhibited excellent reliability, selectivity, and analytical efficiency for the simultaneous estimation of sitagliptin and metformin in combined dosage forms. Careful optimization of chromatographic parameters ensured baseline resolution between both analytes with sharp, symmetric peaks and a satisfactory run time. The use of a reversed-phase C18 column with a judiciously selected mobile phase composition provided highly efficient separation, validating the suitability of the chosen conditions for routine pharmaceutical analysis.

Calibration curves constructed for sitagliptin and metformin across the tested concentration ranges (0.5–50 µg/mL) demonstrated exceptional linearity with correlation coefficients ($r^2 > 0.999$), reflecting the excellent proportional relationship between concentration and detector response. The low intercepts and residual values suggested minimal systematic deviation and robust instrument performance. Comparable results have been reported by Musmade et al [15], and Khan et al [16], who also obtained correlation coefficients above 0.998 for the same combination under similar chromatographic environments. More recently, Mohsin Ali et al [17] and Aqeela Raza et al [13], confirmed analogous

linear trends for sitagliptin–metformin mixtures using slightly modified mobile phase compositions, further substantiating the reproducibility and reliability of the present approach.

Accuracy studies performed at multiple concentration levels yielded recoveries within 98–102%, confirming that excipients or degradation products did not interfere with analyte quantitation. These recovery values are consistent with the findings of Balaji et al [18] and Alshora et al [4], who reported recovery ranges of 98.5–100.8% and emphasized method precision and ruggedness in multi-component assays. Intra-day and inter-day precision values ($RSD < 2\%$) further verified the method's repeatability and intermediate precision, demonstrating consistency across analytical runs. Comparable precision was also documented in recent stability-indicating HPLC studies involving metformin combinations with SGLT-2 inhibitors, where RSD values typically remained below 1% [19].

The limits of detection and quantitation were markedly low, highlighting the method's high sensitivity and suitability for trace-level determination. The LOD and LOQ values are comparable to or slightly superior to those reported by Raza et al [13] and recent metformin–remogliflozin assays, which

achieved LODs near 0.085 µg/mL for metformin using phosphate buffer–acetonitrile systems [20]. Such performance underscores the capability of the developed procedure to detect low analyte concentrations without compromising accuracy or reproducibility.

Robustness evaluation through deliberate variations in flow rate, wavelength, and mobile phase ratio revealed no significant deviations in retention time, resolution, or peak area. This indicates a resilient and stable analytical system that can tolerate minor operational fluctuations. Similar robustness outcomes have been described [21] and by contemporary investigations on metformin–empagliflozin combinations [22], confirming the practical applicability of such methods in routine quality control environments.

Solution stability studies performed over 48 hours showed negligible variation in assay values, confirming the analytes' stability under typical laboratory storage conditions. Stability-indicating performance is in agreement with current trends in chromatographic method development that emphasize the need for stability verification of antidiabetic combinations [23]. The greenness evaluation using the Analytical Eco-Scale and AGREE metrics yielded scores above 75 and 0.8, respectively, categorizing the method as highly eco-friendly. Comparable green chemistry outcomes have been reported for similar analytical protocols optimized to minimize solvent usage and energy consumption [24]. This demonstrates the growing alignment of analytical methodologies with sustainability principles and regulatory expectations for environmentally responsible practices.

Collectively, the validation results confirm that the proposed HPLC procedure fulfills all ICH Q2(R1) criteria regarding linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, robustness, and sensitivity. The integration of high analytical performance with an environmentally considerate design positions this method as a dependable, reproducible, and sustainable approach for the simultaneous quantification of sitagliptin and metformin in bulk and finished pharmaceutical formulations. Given its superior greenness profile and minimal solvent consumption, the developed method represents a

valuable advancement over conventional, solvent-intensive HPLC procedures.

Conclusion

The developed RP-HPLC method proved to be simple, precise, and reliable for the simultaneous estimation of sitagliptin and metformin in combined dosage forms. The procedure met all ICH Q2(R1) validation requirements, demonstrating excellent linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. The method's low detection limits and high recovery rates confirm its sensitivity and suitability for routine quality control as well as stability studies. Furthermore, the favorable greenness scores highlight its environmental compatibility. Overall, the method offers a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to conventional HPLC approaches for simultaneous analysis of sitagliptin and metformin in pharmaceutical preparations

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